

Generic negative scenarios for the specification of collaborative cyber-physical systems

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Supplement

This document provides supplementary materials to V. Stenkova, J. Brings, M. Daun, and T. Weyer, “Generic negative scenarios for the specification of collaborative cyber-physical systems,” presented at the 38th International Conference on Conceptual Modeling (ER 2019), 2019¹. In particular a more extensive description of the case example as well as the detailed application of the approach are presented.

1 Case example

We illustrate the approach using a platooning case example from our industry partners and the specific scenario of faulty traffic sign recognition. In addition, application of the approach to the case example and the respective findings have been discussed with several experts from the industry as well.

1.1 Platooning

A platoon consists of vehicles equipped with cooperative adaptive cruise control systems. These systems enable the vehicles to dynamically form platoons during runtime². In a platoon two major roles can be distinguished: the leading vehicle and the following vehicles. While the leading vehicle is driven manually, initiates maneuvers, and is responsible for the organization of the platoon. The following vehicles automatically follow the vehicle ahead of them and exchange information among each other and the leading vehicle. Therefore, each vehicle can sense its environment and exchange information with the other vehicles to allow the platoon leader to make decisions taking all available context information into account. This allows them to keep a small distance from each other and perform maneuvers together. Platooning offers advantages over single driving such as safety, eco-friendliness, cost savings (time, fuel) as well as advantages for road traffic and the drivers themselves.

1.2 Scenario: Traffic sign recognition

To illustrate the approach, we focus on a particular scenario involving the faulty recognition of a speed limit traffic sign. The recognition of traffic signs depends on many factors, including lighting conditions, weather conditions, obstacles, and the condition of the sensors. Therefore, in a platoon, different vehicles may recognize different speed limits on the same traffic sign or on different traffic signs placed close to each other. In all following scenarios the detailed specification of the traffic sign recognition is simplified to better illustrate our approach.

¹ V. Stenkova, J. Brings, M. Daun, and T. Weyer, “Generic negative scenarios for the specification of collaborative cyber-physical systems,” presented at the 38th International Conference on Conceptual Modeling (ER 2019), 2019.

² V. Milanés, S. E. Shladover, J. Spring, C. Nowakowski, H. Kawazoe, and M. Nakamura, “Cooperative adaptive cruise control in real traffic situations,” *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 296–305, 2014.

2 Generating generic negative scenarios

The approach for generating generic negative scenarios consists of five steps and is illustrated in **Fig. 1**. First a main scenario (MS) is created representing the regular case where the interaction happens as expected. Then classic alternative scenarios (CAS) are derived from the main scenario. These alternative scenarios represent cases where the interaction does not exactly happen as expected still the result is satisfactory. In the third step, alternative configuration scenarios are created for the main scenario and each classic alternative scenario. Alternative configuration scenarios represent the same situations but for system groups with a varying number of systems. In our platoon example this means for platoons with different numbers of vehicles. The main scenario, the classic alternative scenarios, and the alternative configuration scenarios are analyzed to detect possible defects. These kinds of interactions that do not lead to satisfactory results are referred to as negative scenarios. As this leads to a plethora of negative scenarios, similar negative scenarios are grouped and a generic negative scenario is created in the last step, representing negative scenarios for a varying number of systems in the system group in one diagram.

Fig. 1. Generation of generic negative scenarios

In the following sections the steps are illustrated in detail. In Section 2.1 a main scenario is shown. In Section 2.2 one possible classic alternative scenario is presented. Section 2.3 shows alternative configuration scenarios and Section 2.4 shows possible negative scenarios. The resulting generic negative scenario is presented in Section 2.5.

2.1 Main Scenario

A main scenario describes a common interaction that leads to the desired outcome. In our case, we always consider only the smallest number of systems in the main scenario. Since a platoon consists of a leading vehicle (LV) and at least one following vehicle (FV), the following main scenario shown in **Fig. 2** shows the interactions of these two vehicles and one traffic sign. The leading vehicle recognizes the maximal speed posted on the traffic sign. If the current speed of the platoon is higher than the maximum speed allowed, the leading vehicle instructs the following vehicle to reduce its speed to the new current speed. Note that the actual adaption of speed of both vehicles is omitted and only the interactions are shown.

Fig. 2. Main scenario for traffic sign recognition

2.2 Classic alternative scenario

Beside the main scenario alternative interactions might exist that are less common but still lead to a satisfactory outcome. In requirements engineering these are usually referred to as alternative scenarios. To avoid confusion, we will call these kinds of scenarios classic alternative scenarios. The diagram shown in **Fig. 3** shows a classic alternative scenario to the main scenario in **Fig. 2**. Here the following vehicle recognizes the traffic sign and transmits this piece of information to the leading vehicle which in turn informs the following vehicle of the new current speed if necessary. While this case does not conform to what was originally intended, it still leads to the satisfactory result of all vehicles in the platoon driving under the same speed and under the speed limit.

Fig. 3. Classic alternative scenario for traffic sign recognition

2.3 Alternative configuration scenarios

As system groups, such as a platoon of vehicles, are of a dynamic nature and have to cope with systems joining and leaving the group at runtime, it is insufficient to only consider cases with the smallest possible number of systems. To systematically evaluate the behavior of system groups of larger sizes, we define alternative configuration scenarios. Alternative configuration scenarios are created by adding more instances to the main and the classic alternative scenarios.

Fig. 4 shows such an alternative configuration scenario to the main scenario for a platoon consisting of three vehicles. The leading vehicle recognizes the speed limit posted on the traffic sign, compares it to the current speed of the platoon, and informs the vehicle right behind it (FV₁) of the new current speed if necessary. The first following vehicle then informs the second following vehicle (FV₂) of the new speed. A further alternative configuration scenario for a platoon consisting of four vehicles is shown in **Fig. 5**.

Fig. 4. Alternative configuration scenario to the main scenario for a platoon consisting of three vehicles

Fig. 5. Alternative configuration scenario to the main scenario for a platoon consisting of four vehicles

2.4 Negative Scenarios

To detect possible problems that could lead to unwanted behavior of the system group, the main scenario, the classic alternative scenarios, and the alternative configuration scenarios are analyzed with respect to what could go wrong, so the group does no longer exhibit acceptable behavior. This behavior is documented in a negative scenario.

Fig. 6 shows an example for such a negative scenario. The leading vehicle recognizes the traffic sign with a speed limit and, if necessary, transmits the new speed limit to the following vehicle. (This part is identical with the main scenario). Then, however, the following vehicle recognizes the traffic sign but detects a different speed limit and, if necessary, transmits this speed limit to the leading vehicle. This behavior could be caused by a variety of defects, for example, a defective sensor in one vehicle, bad lighting conditions, or a polluted traffic sign. This situation must be considered unwanted as it could lead to the platoon driving faster than the speed limit.

Fig. 6. Negative scenario for a platoon consisting of two vehicles.

In **Fig. 7** the same situation is depicted for a platoon consisting of three vehicles. Each vehicle recognizes a speed limit on the sign. If necessary, the leading vehicle transmits this piece of information to the first following vehicle, which transmits this to the second following vehicle. The speed recognized by the first following vehicle is transmitted to the leading vehicle, which transmits this piece of information back to the first following vehicle, which it then transmits to the second following vehicle. The speed recognized by the second following vehicle is transmitted to the leading vehicle via the first following vehicle, which again transmits this piece of information back to the first following vehicle, which it then transmits to the second following vehicle. If the vehicles recognize different speed limits on the traffic sign, it is unclear to the platoon what the current speed limit is and therefore, what its maximum speed should be.

Fig. 7. Negative scenario for a platoon consisting of three vehicles.

In **Fig. 8** and **Fig. 9** the unwanted behavior for the previously presented negative scenarios is emphasized. In this negative scenario unwanted behavior occurs when the speed of the leading vehicle is overwritten by the following vehicles with a wrong value. **Fig. 8** and **Fig. 9** illustrate the possible combinations of this happening for a platoon of three and four vehicles respectively.

Fig. 8. Unwanted behavior during traffic sign recognition in a platoon consisting of three vehicles.

Fig. 9. Unwanted behavior during traffic sign recognition in a platoon consisting of three vehicles.

The scenario becomes even more complex if different vehicles in the platoon recognize different speed limits on different traffic signs that are placed nearby. This can, for instance, happen if one of the traffic signs was hidden and could not be read by all vehicles. **Fig. 10** illustrates such a negative scenario for a platoon consisting of two vehicles that each recognize different traffic signs (TS₁ and TS₂).

Fig. 11 shows a negative scenario involving a platoon of three cars and two traffic signs. The leading vehicle and the second following vehicle both recognize TS₁, but the first following vehicle recognizes TS₂ which posts a different speed limit than TS₁.

Fig. 10. Negative scenario for platooning consisting of two vehicles recognizing two different traffic signs.

Fig. 11. Negative Scenario for a Platoon consisting of three vehicles recognizing two different traffic signs.

2.5 Generic Negative Scenario

In **Fig. 12** the generic negative scenario for the detection of faulty traffic signs within a platoon is shown. The generic negative scenario abstracts from concrete instances but shows instances for different identified instance classes. Instance classes are *lead vehicle (LV)*, *following vehicle 1 (FV₁)*, *following vehicle 2-n (FV_{2,...,n})* and *traffic signs (TS_{1,...,m})*. Note that due to their high degree of similarity all following vehicles, but the first following vehicle, are grouped into the class *following vehicle 2-n*. In the generic negative scenario, the unwanted behavior, which in this case represents the overwriting of the desired speed of the platoon, is caused by the identified generic instances which means that at least one vehicle in position three or higher detects a wrong speed limit and propagates the wrong speed limit to the entire platoon.

Fig. 12. Generic negative scenario of a platoon detecting speed limits on traffic signs.